

D6.3: Report on XR4HUMAN Experience Library Evaluation & Results

Authors: F. Mushtaq (UoL), O. Schreer (HHI), M. Barngrover (XR4Europe), E. Prasolova-Forland (NTNU), M. Fominykh (NTNU), Hannah Svennungsen (NTNU), Marianna Pizzo (NTNU)

Editors: O. Schreer (HHI), F. Mushtaq (UoL)

Project title: The Equitable, Inclusive, and Human-Centered XR Project

Project acronym: XR4HUMAN

Grant Agreement no.: 101070155
Lead contractor for this deliverable:

Deliverable factsheet:

Project Number:	101070155
Project Acronym:	XR4Human
Project Title:	The Equitable, Inclusive, and Human-Centered XR Project
Title of Deliverable:	D6.3 Experience Library Evaluations & Result
Work Package:	WP6
Due date according to contract:	30. October 2025 (M36)
Editor(s):	O. Schreer (HHI), Faisal Mushtaq (UoL)
Contributor(s):	M. Barngrover (XR4Europe), Ekaterina Prasolova-Forland (NTNU), Mikhail Fominykh (NTNU), Hannah Svenningsen (NTNU), Marianna Pizzo (NTNU), Stig Tobiassen (NTNU)
Reviewer(s):	Lucas Stephane (IFE)
Approved by	Rigmor C. Baraas, Rosemarie Bernabe

ABSTRACT:	This deliverable reports the outcomes of Task 6.4 within Work Package 6 of XR4HUMAN. It documents the development of a standardised, modular post-experience survey for XR evaluation, its piloting in controlled and public settings, and its integration with complementary protocols led by partners, notably NTNU. The report synthesises findings from evaluations conducted with diverse user groups, including children and young people, adults with cognitive or physical impairments, jobseekers engaged through national employment services, international students, and medical students using specialist neuroanatomy applications. Results are presented with a focus on factors that matter for evaluation—onboarding, navigation and orientation, sensory comfort, accessibility, vocational
------------------	---

	<p>relevance, and engagement sustainability—rather than on appraisal of specific applications. The deliverable also describes targeted software re-development to exemplify responsible and inclusive practice; and it sets out a sustainability pathway for the Experience Library, including replication on the XR4Europe website, migration to a lightweight data-collection platform, and a volunteer evaluator pool chaired by XR4Europe. Together, these actions establish an evidence-based, ethically grounded framework for inclusive XR evaluation that can be reused beyond the lifetime of the project.</p>
<p>Keyword List:</p>	<p>XR experience, library, submission form, self-assessment form, evaluation, benchmark</p>

Consortium:

	ROLE	NAME	Short Name	Country
1.	Coordinator	UNIVERSITETET I SOROST-NORGE	USN	NO
2.	Partner	XR4EUROPE	XR4Europe	BE
3.	Partner	UNIVERSITETET I OSLO	UiO	NO
4.	Partner	ETHNICON METSOVION POLYTECHNION	NTUA	EL
5.	Partner	NORGES TEKNISK-NATURVITENSKAPELIGE UNIVERSITET NTNU	NTNU	NO
6.	Partner	UNIVERSITEIT LEIDEN	ULEI	NL
7.	Partner	KARLSRUHER INSTITUT FUER TECHNOLOGIE	KIT	DE
8.	Partner	INSTITUTT FOR ENERGITEKNIKK	IFE	NO
9.	Partner	FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FORDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG EV	Fraunhofer	DE
10.	Partner	OPEN AR CLOUD EUROPE GEMEINNUTZIGE UG	OARC EU	DE
11.	Partner	STICHTING FONTYS	Fontys	NL
12.	AP	UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS	UNIVLEEDS	UK

Revision history:

VERSION	DATE	Revised by	Reason
0.1	12.08.2025	Original version drafted by Faisal Mushtaq	
0.2	26.08.2025	Input by partners	
0.3	15.09.2025	Consolidated version	
0.4	01.10.2025	Internal review	
0.5	16.10.2025	Final version sent to coordinator	
1.0	19.10.2025	Approved by coordinator	

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	6
2	Methodological Framework for Evaluation	8
3	Development of the Post-XR4HUMAN Survey	10
	Rationale and Objectives.....	10
	Literature-Derived Framework	10
	Expert-Led Iterative Refinement	10
	Pilot Testing Across Contrasting Contexts.....	11
	Data Handling and Initial Benchmarking	11
	Summary	13
4	Examples of Real-World Evaluations	14
	Individuals with Cognitive and Physical Impairments.....	15
	Methodology	15
	Results	17
	Vocational and Career Exploration Evaluations.....	18
	Methodology	19
	Results	20
	Implications for Evaluation Frameworks	21
	NAV Jobseeker Evaluations	21
	Methodology	22
	Results	22
	Implications for Evaluation Frameworks.....	23
5	XR Software (Re)-Development	25
	XR software applications VR4VET Blue Sector and Nevrolens.....	25
	VR4VET Blue Sector	25
	Nevrolens.....	26
	XR software refinement use cases and results	26
	Inclusion and Accessibility refinements in the VR4VET Blue Sector app.....	27
	Inclusion and Accessibility refinements in the Nevrolens app	32
	Conclusions of the Software refinement.....	34
6	Experience Library Future	36
	Annex 1: Post-XR Experience Final Survey (Online Version)	39

1 Introduction

This document presents *Deliverable D6.3*, the final report for Work Package 6 (WP6) of the XR4Human project, corresponding to *Task 6.4: Evaluation of Example Use Cases*. As outlined in the Grant Agreement, WP6 focuses on the creation, curation, and responsible dissemination of extended reality (XR) experiences, with Task 6.4 committed specifically to their systematic evaluation. The objective of this task is to assess the quality and accessibility of selected XR experiences across a range of user-centred dimensions, including cybersickness, visual (dis)comfort, accessibility, and perceptions relating to safety, security, privacy, and ethics.

The evaluation work undertaken in this task was designed to produce meaningful benchmark data, grounded in empirical usage within physical XR laboratories. In keeping with the inclusive ethos of XR4Human, the project prioritised the recruitment of participants from under-represented groups, encompassing variation across age, gender, ethnicity, and sensory-motor abilities. This inclusive sampling strategy was essential to ensuring that the evaluations conducted under Task 6.4 are generalisable and reflect the real-world diversity of XR users.

To support the delivery of this task, the consortium developed a dedicated evaluation survey instrument tailored to the dimensions above. The tool was deployed in conjunction with selected submissions from the XR4HUMAN Experience Library, most notably the 'da Vinci' experience, which was evaluated with a benchmark sample of 64 participants (32 adults and 32 children) at the University of Leeds. In parallel, additional pooled data and qualitative evaluations were undertaken by Ekaterina Prasolova-Førland, Mikhail Fominykh and other colleagues at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), providing complementary insights into user experience across use cases.

Throughout this process, WP6 also supported partner institutions in refining their XR submissions to meet the evolving technical and ethical standards of the XR4HUMAN framework. Notably, the NTNU submissions were updated to align with the project's guidelines on non-commercial use, accessibility, and ethical evaluation. External partners, including stakeholders from the Smart City initiative in Kirchheim, Germany (connected via Technische Universität München), were invited to contribute both to the Delphi study on best practices and to the XR4HUMAN Experience Library.

While WP6 as a whole has advanced the design, curation, and dissemination of responsible XR experiences, this document concentrates on how those experiences were evaluated in practice. Section 2 sets out the methodological framework that underpins core activities in Task 6.4. Section 3 details the development of the post-experience survey and explains how the literature-derived constructs and expert iterations shaped a modular instrument. Section 4 presents real-world evaluations across multiple settings and participant groups, with an emphasis on the factors that evaluation must capture to remain inclusive and generalisable. Section 5 summarises targeted software re-development carried out to align exemplar

experiences with XR4HUMAN guidance. Section 6 outlines the sustainability plan for the Experience Library.

2 Methodological Framework for Evaluation

A key objective of Task 6.4 was to establish a robust and replicable methodology for evaluating XR experiences in ways that are both user-centred and technically informative. Central to this was the development of a standardised post-experience survey instrument that could be deployed across different XR use cases and institutional contexts. The motivation for this was twofold: to ensure consistency in how XR experiences are assessed across the XR4Human consortium, and to generate benchmark data that could support meaningful comparisons over time and between applications.

The lack of standardisation in how XR experiences are currently evaluated poses a challenge to both research and practice. While many studies focus on technical performance or subjective impressions, fewer adopt a unified approach that incorporates ethical, psychological, and accessibility-oriented dimensions within a single evaluation framework. This gap was particularly evident when trying to compare or interpret user responses across different environments, technologies, or user populations. Without a common instrument, data remained siloed or anecdotal, limiting the extent to which we could draw generalisable insights or identify patterns of harm, discomfort, or exclusion.

To address this, WP6 designed a modular survey (see Annex 1: Post-XR Experience Final Survey (Online Version)) that could be used after any XR experience has been delivered in person. The survey was structured around key dimensions specified in the Grant Agreement: cybersickness, visual comfort, physical and cognitive accessibility, and perceived ratings of security, safety, privacy, and ethical integrity. Additional items were included to capture users' demographic background, prior XR familiarity, and any specific barriers encountered during the experience. This structure allows the survey to serve not only as a user feedback tool but also as a vehicle for surfacing normative issues in XR design.

Standardisation brings several key advantages. It enables data aggregation across sites, populations, and technologies, thus supporting the generation of pooled datasets that can be meaningfully analysed. It also enhances transparency and accountability, as developers contributing to the Experience Library can be evaluated along consistent criteria. Perhaps most importantly, it provides a foundation for benchmarking: identifying where particular applications excel or fall short in meeting inclusive and ethical design standards. In the context of XR4Human, this approach reinforces the project's commitment to responsible innovation and provides a methodological anchor for future XR research that seeks to centre the lived experience of diverse users.

The methodological framework therefore rests on two pillars: a common, construct-based survey that provides comparable post-experience data across sites, and context-sensitive protocols that capture observational and task-based indicators where these are most informative. Having established the need for a standardized evaluation approach, the next step was to develop the specific survey

instrument that would operationalise this framework. The survey development process involved literature synthesis, expert iteration and pilot testing to create a robust and modular measurement tool that could be deployed across multiple use cases, such as a public exhibition and a specialist clinical training lab, while maintaining construct comparability.

3 Development of the Post-XR4HUMAN Survey

A core component of Task 6.4 has been the design and refinement of a standardised, cross-domain questionnaire for evaluating user experience in XR environments. The objective is to provide the XR4HUMAN consortium with a robust, adaptable measurement tool that can be applied across multiple use cases while supporting modular tailoring to specific contexts or participant groups.

Rationale and Objectives

XR technologies are increasingly deployed in education, healthcare, vocational training, and other domains, yet existing evaluation practices remain inconsistent. Studies often use ad hoc or domain-specific measures, making it difficult to compare findings or synthesise evidence through meta-analysis. XR4HUMAN seeks to address this fragmentation by producing a standardised instrument grounded in evidence-based constructs, capable of capturing the breadth of user experience while remaining sensitive to context-specific needs. The tool's design also prioritises inclusivity, ensuring that items are clear and accessible to diverse participant groups, including those with limited prior XR exposure.

Literature-Derived Framework

The foundation of the instrument was established through the literature review and analysis reported in Deliverable D7.1. This process synthesised evidence from 168 XR-related studies, identifying 38 that employed post-experience questionnaires suitable for detailed construct analysis. From these, six recurring constructs emerged as critical for XR evaluation: presence, physical comfort, usability, intention to use, cognitive load, and satisfaction. These constructs form the conceptual backbone of the XR4HUMAN instrument. The methodology for this construct extraction is described in detail in D7.1.

Expert-Led Iterative Refinement

Building on the D7.1 framework, the WP6 team undertook four structured rounds of expert review and refinement. Each iteration involved:

- Mapping existing items against the six constructs to identify underrepresented areas and redundant coverage.
- Integrating validated items from established tools such as NASA-TLX, ITC-SOPI, and UEQ to strengthen construct validity, particularly in the domains of presence and cognitive load, as well as additional self-efficacy and accessibility items
- Refining item wording to ensure clarity, neutrality, and cross-domain applicability.
- Reviewing construct coherence, item sequence, and response format to optimise participant engagement and minimise survey fatigue.

This process was collaborative and multidisciplinary, with feedback loops between domain experts, human factors specialists, and XR practitioners ensuring that the instrument balanced psychometric rigour with practical usability.

Pilot Testing Across Contrasting Contexts

The refined survey was piloted in two markedly different evaluation contexts. The first was a large public-facing event, in which participants were primarily children and teenagers interacting with XR in a bustling, informal setting. Here, paper-based surveys were used for accessibility, and participants often required parental assistance or researcher guidance to complete items. The second was a controlled laboratory study with adult participants, where the survey was delivered electronically via Qualtrics and participants had uninterrupted time to respond independently. These contrasting settings enabled assessment of the survey’s applicability across different age groups, XR experience levels, and environmental conditions.

Data Handling and Initial Benchmarking

Responses from both pilots were merged into a unified dataset. Data cleaning included exclusion of questionnaires with no post-experience responses, reverse-coding of negatively worded items, and mapping of all items to their respective constructs. Likert-scale responses were converted to numerical values for analysis, and partial completions were retained to allow examination of non-response patterns as indicators of usability challenges.

Descriptive statistics summarised participant demographics, completion rates, and item-level response patterns. Notably, completion rates differed sharply between contexts, with the controlled laboratory setting achieving over 95% completion, compared to around 60% in the public event. Items linked to cognitive load saw disproportionately high non-completion among younger participants, suggesting that further simplification or rewording may be required for this demographic.

The Table 1 summarizes the demographic characteristics of the participants in the two groups. There was a significant difference in age composition between the two samples: the public event sample was mainly composed of children aged 10-17 years (93.8%), while the Lab sample was mainly composed of young people aged 18-29 years (90.3%). The gender distribution showed a slight female majority in both groups (60% overall). Regarding experience with XR, 84% of participants reported limited exposure, of whom 35% had never experienced XR technology and 49% had only tried it once or twice. Only 3% were long-term users. This distribution characteristic reflects the current state of XR applications, where most users are still in the preliminary exploration stage despite growing interest (Wang et al., 2024).

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Variable	Category	Public Event	Laboratory	Total n (%)
----------	----------	--------------	------------	-------------

Age Group	10 or Under	16	0	16 (26)
	11-17	14	0	14 (22)
	18-29	1	28	29 (46)
	30-39	0	2	2 (3)
	40-49	1	1	2 (3)
Gender	Female	16	22	38 (60)
	Male	15	9	24 (38)
	Prefer not to say	1	0	1 (2)
XR Experience	Never tried before			
	Tried once or twice	11	11	22 (35)
	Occasional use (few times a year)	16	15	31 (49)
	Regular use (a few times a month)	2	4	6 (10)
		1	1	2 (3)
	No answer	2	0	2 (3)

Note. Percentages are based on valid responses.

Table 2 Item-Level Descriptives (Means and Standard Deviations). (R) indicates reverse coded to aid interpretation.

	Public Event			Lab			Total		
	Mean	N	SD	Mean	N	SD	Mean	N	SD
Enjoyment	4.00	30	0.743	4.00	31	0.816	4.00	61	0.775
Easy of Use	3.47	30	1.042	3.77	31	0.762	3.62	61	0.916
Device suitability	3.76	29	0.636	3.74	31	0.855	3.75	60	0.751
Full immersive	3.60	30	1.003	3.77	31	0.762	3.69	61	0.886
Phys. demand (R)	3.50	28	1.291	3.35	31	0.950	3.42	59	1.117
Phys. discomfort (R)	4.30	30	1.088	3.35	31	1.112	3.82	61	1.190
Mental Demand (R)	2.36	28	1.471	2.81	31	1.078	2.59	59	1.288
Attention attracted	3.69	29	0.806	4.10	31	0.700	3.90	60	0.775
Task Success	3.43	28	1.136	3.35	31	0.950	3.39	59	1.034
Recommendation	3.96	24	0.624	4.13	31	0.670	4.05	55	0.650
Nav. Confidence	3.80	25	1.041	3.52	31	1.029	3.64	56	1.034
Expectation improvement	3.54	24	0.588	4.06	31	0.727	3.84	55	0.714
Privacy Concern (R)	3.50	24	1.351	3.48	31	1.338	3.49	55	1.332
Close to everyday use	<u>3.29</u>	<u>24</u>	<u>1.197</u>	<u>3.03</u>	<u>31</u>	<u>1.329</u>	<u>3.15</u>	<u>55</u>	<u>1.268</u>

Summary

The survey development process has delivered a standardised and adaptable instrument that can serve as the backbone for XR usability evaluation across XR4HUMAN. Its grounding in literature-derived constructs ensures conceptual robustness, while the multi-round expert refinement guarantees practical relevance across diverse domains. The modular format allows the survey to be shortened or expanded depending on context, making it particularly well-suited to Task 6.4's remit of inclusive, generalisable evaluation. The initial benchmark dataset now provides a reference point for future deployments, enabling the programme to track changes in user experience profiles across sites, applications, and participant groups over time.

Together, the four rounds of expert review and the pilot deployments established both feasibility and scope for modular deployment. With the instrument in place, Task 6.4 proceeded to apply the framework across contrasting contexts. The following section presents those evaluations, demonstrating how the standardized survey (with additional questions on accessibility and self-efficacy adjusted for different populations) instrument performs in real-world settings and what these activities reveal about the factors that XR evaluation must address to ensure validity, inclusivity, and reusability of results. Rather than simply reporting individual study outcomes, the focus remains on identifying the methodological, practical, and experiential factors that an effective evaluation framework must capture across diverse populations and contexts.

4 Examples of Real-World Evaluations

The survey development provided XR4HUMAN with a structured tool for consistently measuring user experience. The evaluations described here were not intended to judge individual applications, but to understand what makes XR experiences fair and accessible across different users and settings. Each study therefore outlines its methods, participants, and key findings in relation to the evaluation dimensions introduced earlier. When specific applications are mentioned, they serve only as examples to illustrate key aspects of evaluation such as onboarding, navigation, sensory and cognitive load, accessibility, vocational relevance, and sustained engagement.

The sub-sections that follow cover work with individuals with cognitive and physical impairments, vocational and career exploration deployments in public and laboratory settings, evaluations with jobseekers engaged through (Norwegian Labour and Welfare Administration) NAV, and a hospital-based specialist deployment for medical students learning neuroanatomy. In each case, the emphasis remains on what the evaluations tell us about how to evaluate XR in a robust and inclusive way.

However, its practical deployment in Task 6.4 also required careful alignment with modular evaluation frameworks developed by other partners. A central example of this integration was the work led by NTNU, whose evaluation protocols with the focus on accessibility and inclusivity were designed to ensure that XR4HUMAN's usability and impact measures were both methodologically robust and sensitive to the specific objectives of each pilot. These additional evaluation modules could be included in the XR4HUMAN survey depending on the context, e.g. performing evaluations with users with special needs.

As part of Task 6.4, partners at NTNU conducted a series of evaluations to assess XR experiences across diverse contexts, participant profiles, and application types. These activities broadened the inclusivity of the benchmarking dataset and extended the evaluation framework to vocational, clinical, and accessibility-focused settings. Following the general survey-based methodology outlined earlier in this deliverable, NTNU's work applied a modular approach, tailoring evaluation tools to suit the specific characteristics of each user group while maintaining core objectives related to usability, accessibility, safety, and user experience.

The evaluations spanned five main activity streams: (i) work with individuals with cognitive impairments and physical disabilities, (ii) large-scale public demonstrations at vocational and career events, (iii) structured trials with international students, (iv) targeted sessions with jobseekers in employment support programmes, and (v) assessments in a hospital setting. The findings from these evaluations offer both quantitative indicators and rich qualitative insights into how XR applications perform across varying user capabilities, environments, and technical setups.

Individuals with Cognitive and Physical Impairments

This strand of work at NTNU addressed one of the most critical aims of Task 6.4: to ensure that XR benchmarking activities are grounded in the experiences of participants whose needs and capabilities differ from those of the general population. Specifically, the evaluation sought to understand how individuals with diagnosed cognitive impairments — and in one case an individual with a significant physical disability requiring full-time wheelchair use — experienced XR technologies. The work was motivated by the recognition that for XR to achieve the inclusivity aspirations of the XR4HUMAN programme, evaluation processes must capture not only the successes of the technology for “average” users but also its limitations, risks, and potential adaptations for those with additional support needs.

Methodology

The evaluation took place in NTNU’s dedicated VR laboratory, a space equipped with high-performance VR-capable PCs, head-mounted displays (HMDs), and configurable play areas that could accommodate both standing and seated use. Prior to participant arrival, the environment was prepared to minimise physical hazards, with cables secured and clear walkways maintained. Informed consent procedures were completed in collaboration with participants, caregivers or assistants, who remained present throughout the sessions to provide physical and communicative support as required.

Participants with cognitive impairments were recruited through local support services and day programmes for adults with cognitive impairments. They had been briefed in advance about the nature of the activities, with information provided through their assistants, in accessible language and pictorial form. Upon arrival, participants were introduced to the VR equipment and the VR lab, including safety and hygiene protocols.

Three applications were selected for their contrasting interaction styles and complexity. The first was Purrfect Pop, a hand-tracking game designed around simple and natural gestures. Players face a virtual shelf where cats and flowers appear, touching the cats makes them pop and increases the score, while touching flowers has no penalty (Pizzo et al., 2025)¹. The second was the VR4VET Blue Sector VR app (Fominykh and Prasolova-Førland, 2024)², a career guidance and vocational

¹ Marianna Pizzo, Matteo Martini, Fabio Solari, and Manuela Chessa (2025): Immersive versus Non-Immersive Virtual Reality Environments: Comparing Different Visualization Modalities in a Cognitive-Motor Dual-Task. In Proceedings of the 20th International Joint Conference on Computer Vision, Imaging and Computer Graphics Theory and Applications - Volume 1 GRAPP, HUCAPP and IVAPP: HUCAPP, 561-568, 2025, Porto, Portugal. DOI: [10.5220/0013133600003912](https://doi.org/10.5220/0013133600003912)

² Mikhail Fominykh and Ekaterina Prasolova-Førland (2024): Supporting Career Guidance and Vocational Training in Fishery and Maritime Professions with Virtual Reality. In the 10th International Conference of the Immersive Learning Research Network iLRN Conference, Glasgow, United Kingdom, June 10–13, 2024. Immersive Learning Research Network Practitioner Proceedings. pp. 1–3. DOI: [10.56198/5M1RH0QNF](https://doi.org/10.56198/5M1RH0QNF).

training simulation, which presented a cognitively and motorically demanding environment in which users completed tasks associated with aquaculture and fisheries work, including moving between stations using a teleportation mechanic, manipulating tools with handheld controllers, and interpreting in-world prompts (app presented later in the deliverable). The third app was AR app Nevrolens³ for visualizing rat brain neuroanatomy, presented later in this deliverable, deployed on both HoloLens and on a tablet. While this app has been primarily developed for medical and neuroscience students, we demoed it with individuals with cognitive impairments to explore how AR interfaces, multimodal interaction, and engaging visualizations could support enjoyable and accessible learning experiences across diverse user groups.

The evaluation protocol followed a consistent structure for each participant. The session began with a short verbal introduction to the activity, often with the assistance of the caretaker. This was followed by the fitting of the HMD, and — where relevant — calibration of the hand-tracking system. Each application was demonstrated briefly by the assistant or evaluator, after which the participant was encouraged to take control and interact independently for up to ten minutes. Other participants could follow the activities on laptop or big screen connected to the headsets while waiting for their turn. Observers documented the participant's ability to navigate, initiate actions, and respond to virtual stimuli. Behavioural cues such as facial expression, vocalisation, body posture, and frequency of assistance requests were noted. The same process was repeated for the next application, with a short break in between to avoid fatigue.

Following the lab visits, semi-structured interviews were conducted with a physical impairment participant and the cognitive impairment assistants. The interview of the physical impairment person focused on accessibility, embodiment, and empowerment. Users with cognitive impairments were not interviewed due to practical limitations and ethical considerations related to obtaining informed consent. They were presented with a highly simplified pictorial shortened version of the XR4HUMAN questionnaire instead.

The cognitive impairment assistants were asked about their perceptions of the participant's engagement, inclusion, accessibility and challenges, and the fit between the XR activities and the participant's usual abilities. Qualitative approach was especially useful in this case as the participants' impairments and diagnoses varied significantly. For ethical and privacy reasons, the researchers did not have access to diagnoses, so perceptions and observations of their assistants provided valuable insights on various aspects of cognitively challenged participants' interaction with XR. Interviews were audio-recorded and later summarised thematically. Observational notes, questionnaire results and interview summaries were reviewed together to identify recurring patterns in both opportunities and challenges presented by the XR experiences.

³ Nevrolens <https://www.ntnu.edu/imtel/nevrolens>

Results

The results from this evaluation were complex, illustrating both the empowering potential of XR and the barriers that can limit its accessibility, especially for neurodiverse populations and people with mobility challenges whose needs are often overlooked by developers of XR systems

For the wheelchair-using participant (NTNU employee), the physical embodiment of VR proved to be a double-edged sword. While exploring the Blue Sector environment, the participant leaned forward in his chair to interact with an object on a virtual workbench, overestimating the stability of his real-world position. Immersed in the simulation and momentarily unaware of his physical surroundings, he tipped sideways and partially out of his wheelchair. The assistant intervened immediately, helping him back to the chair, but the event was a clear reminder that immersive XR can generate physical behaviours with real-world consequences, especially for users with limited core stability. According to the participant, the stability also depends on the type of wheelchair used, something that needs to take into account. Following the incident, the participant resumed the activity without hesitation, later describing the experience as “freeing” and unlike anything he could typically do in daily life. This comment reflected a key theme across the evaluations: for some individuals with disabilities, XR offered a form of agency and exploration that transcended their usual physical limitations.

For the participants with cognitive impairments the hand-tracking cat game consistently elicited positive affective responses. Participants smiled, laughed, and experimented with different gestures, quickly learning that the virtual cat would react to their hand movements. The lack of controllers removed a substantial barrier for those with fine motor difficulties or who might be intimidated by unfamiliar hardware. Observers recorded longer uninterrupted play sequences, fewer calls for assistance, and a greater degree of self-initiated exploration compared to the more complex simulation. This sense of immersion, coupled with the simplicity of the interaction, made the cat game a particularly effective example of accessible XR design.

The Blue Sector app highlighted several accessibility and usability challenges for the cognitive impairment group. The teleportation-based movement system was a particular point of difficulty. Participants often struggled to align the controller precisely to the intended destination, and the cognitive demand of remembering multiple buttons and triggers led to frequent pauses and confusion. Assistants found themselves offering near-continuous verbal guidance to maintain forward progress. In several cases, participants became “stuck” in a virtual space, unable to recall the sequence of actions needed to proceed, which occasionally triggered visible frustration — such as lowering the headset, sighing, or disengaging from the controls. Task complexity also compounded the navigation challenges; when an action required more than two or three sequential steps, participants were more likely to lose track of their objective and abandon the attempt. This correlates with

existing research on the use of XR controllers and associated accessibility challenges (ref.)

At the same time, some participants were visibly intrigued by the simulated industrial environment, particularly when guided by a virtual assistant (NPC). They also remarked that if the tools were simpler and the places to go more obvious, it would have been easier: “if you have to navigate over larger areas, where you have to teleport or do things like that, it's difficult for some people to realise that, when they try different things, there are slightly different mechanisms at play, and that's what makes it difficult for them.” This indicates that the setting itself was motivating but the interface presented a barrier. Similarly, participants found the rat brain visualization stimulating, but most of them found it easier to explore the app on the tablet compared to the HoloLens.

A cross-cutting observation from assistants was the importance of predictability and consistency. Participants with cognitive impairments tended to thrive when the environment and task structure remained stable, with cues repeated in the same format and location. Sudden changes in scene or interaction style — for example, shifting from teleportation movement to object manipulation with no transition — could be disorienting and sometimes led to withdrawal from the task. An important aspect when it comes to cognitive impairment group is the individual differences: “Some need constant guidance and repetition, while others understand things right away”. Assistants recommended that future designs incorporate optional “slow mode” features, allowing users to proceed at their own pace without time pressure or the risk of virtual penalties for mistakes.

Overall, the evaluation underscored that XR for individuals with cognitive and physical impairments must be approached with careful attention to both safety and design simplicity. When interaction mechanics are intuitive, feedback is immediate, and the environment is forgiving, participants can engage with a sense of joy and agency. Conversely, when complexity, precision, or multi-step memory demands are high, the risk of disengagement — or, in physical terms, unsafe movements — increases. The lessons from this work will inform XR4HUMAN's inclusive benchmarking framework, ensuring that evaluation criteria capture the nuanced interplay between capability, design, and experience quality for under-represented user groups. Also, there is a need to develop alternative evaluation forms adjusted for diverse groups such as simplified pictorial surveys. To capture in depth the challenges and the needs of the diverse groups, quantitative evaluations are not always sufficient and often need to be supplied with qualitative ones.

Vocational and Career Exploration Evaluations

The NTNU evaluation activities in vocational and career exploration contexts were designed to examine how XR experiences can be assessed in a way that is adaptable to varied settings, participant profiles, and levels of environmental

control. The purpose was not to appraise individual applications in isolation, but to identify the methodological, practical, and experiential factors that an effective evaluation framework must address when applied to XR for vocational awareness, industry outreach, and career guidance.

Two contrasting contexts were used: a high-traffic public engagement environment at the Tautdanning career fair, and a structured laboratory session for international students at NTNU. Together, these settings provided insight into how environmental conditions and participant characteristics shape the feasibility and appropriateness of different evaluation measures.

Methodology

At the career fair, the evaluation was embedded in NTNU's booth over two full days. The Tautdanning education and career fair in Trondheim is one of Norway's largest arenas for students exploring study and vocational opportunities. It gathers universities, colleges, companies, and organizations, offering young people direct insights into different career paths and educational programs. The booth contained two VR stations equipped with high-performance laptops, tethered head-mounted displays, and handheld controllers preloaded with the Blue Sector vocational training application. Recruitment was opportunistic: participants were drawn from the steady flow of visitors, most of whom were secondary school students, early-career adults, or educators attending the fair. Totally 24 participants mostly in the age group 14-17, participated in the evaluation.

The evaluation process was adapted to the public nature of the event. Onboarding began with a concise verbal introduction from a staff member. Session lengths were capped at approximately 10-20 minutes per user to maximise throughput. Staff monitored each session closely, offering brief instructions when participants hesitated or deviated from the intended activity sequence. Data collection relied on questionnaire (standard XR4HUMAN one with additional questions on accessibility, self-efficacy and career guidance) and semi-structured interview involving 2 participants

The second session did not have the same time and space limitations and, allowed for a more systematic evaluation, taking place in the lab and nearby classroom where the students (aged 18 +) received XR4HUMAN presentation prior to the evaluation. This session involved 28 international students, attending ISFIT festival in Trondheim. The XR laboratory and classroom provided a controlled space with adjustable lighting and ample room for standing or seated play. After an initial project briefing, participants rotated between several XR applications, with most spending at least 15 minutes in the Blue Sector environment.

The evaluation process in the lab included:

1. **Pre-experience briefing** explaining the purpose of the activity and the basic controls.

2. **Researcher-led onboarding** using both verbal instruction and demonstration inside the headset.
3. **Post-experience** questionnaire consisting selected questions from the standard XR4HUMAN survey plus additional questions on accessibility, self-efficacy and career guidance.

Results

The evaluations in both contexts revealed several factors that any XR evaluation in vocational contexts must capture, each illustrated through concrete observations.

Based on the interviews conducted at the career fair, students generally found the Blue sector app to be user-friendly, particularly those with prior gaming experience. Both students reported that the use of controllers was intuitive, especially with the help of clear labeling and an introductory tutorial. Virtual guides (NPCs) were seen as helpful in explaining tasks and maintaining flow, although one student believed they could manage without them, albeit more slowly. Text was easy to read in VR, and the addition of text-to-speech was considered a useful feature. One participant suggested that improved graphics could enhance the experience, particularly for extended use.

In terms of learning outcomes and vocational exploration, both students felt that VR provided valuable insights into the industry and could complement physical practice. One student noted that they learned more about factory work rather than traditional aquaculture settings, while the other emphasized that VR could increase accessibility and inclusion, especially as technology becomes more affordable and widespread. Elements like directional arrows and interactive guidance contributed to a sense of mastery and engagement. Overall, both students expressed a high level of confidence in using the VR app, with potential for increased self-efficacy and motivation through further experience.

Approachability and onboarding emerged as decisive in the career fair environment. Many participants at the booth had no prior VR experience and some required reassurance before agreeing to participate. Staff presence and approachable physical setup reduced hesitation. For evaluation purposes, this suggests that measuring both *time-to-engagement* and the *number of onboarding interventions* could serve as robust indicators of accessibility in public-facing contexts. Both groups (career fair and International Students) answered the **Blue Sector questionnaire, including XR4HUMAN questions**. Key takeaways:

The Blue Sector VR app was evaluated positively by both groups of students. Most respondents agreed that the app was easy to use, with the controls and interface generally perceived as intuitive. Confidence in navigating the environment was also rated highly, suggesting that even participants with limited VR experience were able to engage effectively with the simulation. In terms of learning outcomes, a strong majority reported that the app gave them new insights into aquaculture and fisheries, and many saw clear potential for such tools to complement more traditional forms of vocational training. Motivation and engagement scores were

also high, with students describing the experience as enjoyable and stimulating for further exploration of the sector.

Although the overall pattern of responses was clearly positive, the charts also showed some variation. A minority of students remained neutral or less certain about their level of autonomy in the app, pointing to areas where navigation and task flow may be further refined. Similarly, while most participants endorsed the educational and vocational value of the app, a small proportion were less convinced, highlighting the importance of continued development and testing with diverse user groups. Taken together, the results suggest that the Blue Sector app provides an effective and engaging introduction to fisheries and aquaculture, with strong potential for use in vocational guidance and education, while also leaving room for targeted improvements.

Blue Sector has also undergone extensive testing in schools and at career fairs in Shetland, UK, where it demonstrated clear impact and received positive feedback. However, the outcomes of these evaluations fall outside the scope of this deliverable.

Implications for Evaluation Frameworks

These findings confirm that vocational XR evaluations must be methodologically flexible while maintaining a set of core measures. Factors such as onboarding clarity, navigation success, sensory comfort, accessibility, utility, vocational relevance, and engagement sustainability can be measured across settings, but the instruments and scoring rubrics should be modular.

NAV Jobseeker Evaluations

The NAV jobseeker evaluations formed a key part of NTNU's contribution to Task 6.4 by extending XR4HUMAN's evaluation activities into the context of employment preparation and vocational re-entry. Conducted in collaboration with the Norwegian Labour and Welfare Administration (NAV), these sessions provided an opportunity to examine how XR evaluation frameworks operate when the target audience includes individuals actively seeking work, often with varied educational backgrounds, mental health and social issues, differing digital literacy levels, and diverse motivational profiles.

The purpose of these evaluations was not to assess the intrinsic quality of the XR content alone, but to identify which factors in the evaluation process are most relevant when assessing XR as a tool for jobseeker engagement and skills awareness. The NAV context is particularly instructive because it brings together participants, in particular vulnerable youth, who may face structural barriers to employment and for whom accessibility, clarity, and perceived relevance are central to sustained engagement.

Methodology

The evaluations were conducted at a NAV centre equipped with a designated demonstration area that could accommodate small groups. Participants were recruited from active NAV jobseeker lists, with invitations extended to those attending scheduled career support sessions. Recruitment was therefore pragmatic and contextually embedded, meaning participants represented a realistic cross-section of the service user base rather than a self-selected technology-enthusiast population. Some of the participants had mental health issues, including one with autism diagnosis.

Evaluation ran in 2 blocks on 1 day, with 5 designated stations with the Blue Sector vocational training experience, to avoid waiting and provide a comfortable and dignified user experience. To facilitate a participant with autism, an individual station was set up in a separate room to avoid sensory overload, where the participant could try the app with the help from NTNU researcher and career counsellor. Headsets and controllers were sanitised between uses. Each individual session lasted approximately 10-20 minutes, balancing the need for a meaningful exploration of the different parts of the app with the need to avoid fatigue and sensory overload.

The evaluation protocol comprised:

- Pre-session briefing to introduce XR, explain the activity, and clarify safety considerations.
- Guided onboarding with a researcher fitting the headset, explaining the controllers, and initiating the experience.
- Immediate quantitative survey for participants after the sessions, including XR4HUMAN general questions and questions in accessibility, self-efficacy and career guidance aspects.
- Qualitative data were captured through focus group interview with 5 participants, and focus group with 5 counsellors

Results

The NAV sessions brought to light several key considerations for evaluating XR technologies in jobseeker contexts, combining insights from both qualitative and quantitative data

The NAV sessions provided valuable insights into how XR technologies like the Blue Sector VR app function in career guidance for jobseekers. Drawing on qualitative data from focus group interviews with users and counsellors, alongside quantitative feedback collected immediately after user sessions, the app was generally described as engaging and curiosity-provoking.

Many users reported that the immersive format helped them visualize work tasks and better understand job roles. Counsellors, meanwhile, observed increased initiative and physical involvement, particularly among participants who had previously been passive or hesitant. However, some inconsistencies between

qualitative and quantitative findings suggest that user perceptions may shift depending on context, timing, and the type of feedback elicited. A key factor influencing engagement was vocational relevance. While some users felt the experience closely mirrored real work and sparked greater interest in the profession, others struggled to connect the virtual tasks to their own career goals. This variation highlights the need to assess not only perceived realism but also personal applicability—whether users see the activity as relevant to their employment trajectory. Here, the counsellor’s role was essential in helping users interpret the experience and relate it to their individual career paths.

Digital confidence varied across both users and counsellors. Although most users had prior exposure to VR, the time and support needed to get started differed significantly. This underscores the importance of evaluating initial confidence and support load, especially when working with individuals who may not identify as digitally adept.

Physical discomfort was minimal, though a few users required headset adjustments due to glasses, and one participant shortened their session due to headset weight. These findings suggest that ergonomics—headset fit, controller grip, and seating should be considered in future evaluations.

Accessibility and inclusion features played a significant role in shaping the user experience. Tools such as text-to-speech, virtual guides, controller labelling, and high-contrast text were generally well received and often used voluntarily. However, qualitative interviews revealed mixed reactions—some users found these features helpful, while others experienced confusion or sensory overload. This points to the importance of flexible, user-centred design that accommodates diverse needs.

Navigation and task comprehension were mostly smooth, supported by a clear tutorial. Still, some users needed verbal prompts, often due to unfamiliarity with the vocational (fishery) setting rather than interface design. Counsellors and assistants were instrumental in helping users overcome these challenges, reinforcing the importance of relational support in XR-based career guidance.

Ultimately, while the BlueSector app shows strong potential to spark engagement and support experiential learning, its success depends not only on the technology itself but also on the relational, adaptive, and inclusive frameworks that surround it.

Implications for Evaluation Frameworks

The NAV jobseeker evaluations show that when XR is deployed in employment support settings, evaluation frameworks must account for a broader spectrum of user readiness, comfort, and motivation than in more homogenous participant groups. Factors such as onboarding support load, ergonomic comfort, navigation confidence, personal applicability, voluntary use of accessibility features, and engagement drivers can all influence both the experience and the data collected. The methodological takeaway is that evaluation instruments must be sensitive enough to capture these dimensions without imposing additional barriers to

participation, particularly in populations where confidence and trust in digital tools cannot be assumed. In addition, special adjustments need to be considered to participants with mental and physical health challenges that are often overrepresented in this user group.

Medical student evaluation

The study was conducted at Levanger Hospital on March 11, 2025, with 8 participants aged 18–29 (6 female, 2 male). Most participants used glasses or contact lenses, while none reported hearing impairments. Educational backgrounds ranged from high school to bachelor's degree. They were presented with updated Nevrolens application and selected questions from the XR4HUMAN survey + accessibility questions. The results are summarized below:

The survey results showed that participants generally found the scalable text size and contrast modes useful. Adjusting brightness and font size was reported to reduce strain during longer sessions. Although no severe visual impairments were represented, the flexibility of these features was considered important even for mild vision correction.

Speech clarity and the availability of captions or subtitles were highlighted as positive additions. While none of the participants reported hearing loss, captions were noted as helpful in noisy environments or when audio quality was less than ideal, suggesting broader benefits beyond users with diagnosed impairments.

Simplified navigation menus and clearer iconography were reported to improve ease of use. Icons were described as easier to distinguish, which helped reduce cognitive load. A centralized accessibility menu was also valued, as it allowed adjustments such as contrast, text scaling, and captions to be toggled quickly without interrupting the main task flow.

At the same time, several limitations emerged. Participants often struggled to activate the text-to-speech function, and once running, the audio could not be stopped, which many found frustrating. Model manipulation was another challenge: users sometimes confused moving the entire brain with individual parts, and controls for whole-model adjustments were hidden behind menus.

Overall, despite these challenges, the findings suggest that the new accessibility features represent meaningful progress and provide a strong foundation for future improvements.

5 XR Software (Re)-Development

As part of WP6's iterative approach, two submissions from the Experience Library were supported through targeted refinements to demonstrate alignment with XR4HUMAN's principles on inclusivity, accessibility, and ethical self-assessment. The intent was not to redesign the applications wholesale, but to surface practical changes that improve evaluability and user experience in line with the methodology set out in Sections 2–4.

XR software applications VR4VET Blue Sector and Nevrolens

This subsection provides a brief description of the two XR software applications that were refined to demonstrate alignment with XR4HUMAN's principles.

VR4VET Blue Sector

The VR4VET Blue Sector VR app^{4,5,6} is being developed for career guidance and vocational training in the Blue Economy sector, with a focus on empowering young job seekers (Fominykh and Prasolova-Førland, 2024)⁷.

Figure 1 Screenshot of the Blue Sector VR Experience

⁴ VR4VET Blue Sector on Meta App store, <https://www.meta.com/en-gb/experiences/vr4vet-blue-sector/7304270832929125/>

⁵ The development of the VR4VET Blue Sector app was supported by the Virtual Reality for Vocational Education and Training - [VR4VET project](#), partially funded by the European Union's Erasmus Plus program, grant number [2021-1-NO01-KA220-VET-000028033](#).

⁶ The development of the VR4VET Blue Sector app was supported by UHI Shetland and the Department for Environment, Food, and Rural Affairs in respect of a project titled UK Seafood Fund – Skills and Training Pillar (Grant) Round 1.

⁷ Mikhail Fominykh and Ekaterina Prasolova-Førland (2024): Supporting Career Guidance and Vocational Training in Fishery and Maritime Professions with Virtual Reality. In the 10th International Conference of the Immersive Learning Research Network, Glasgow, UK. DOI: [10.56198/5M1RH0QNF](https://doi.org/10.56198/5M1RH0QNF).

The app simulates an area of a fjord with several fish cages, a fish feeding station, a fish health and welfare station, a fish processing facility, a fish laboratory, and a reception area. The users can experience situations representing typical workplaces in the aquaculture and fish processing industries, such as feeding fish, inspecting fish for injuries and diseases, sorting fish in a factory, and analysing water samples in a fish laboratory.

Nevrolens

Nevrolens AR app^{8,9} is a collaborative AR neuroanatomy education tool that allows learners to inspect and manipulate a rat brain and the human brain model (Fominykh et al., 2024)¹⁰.

Figure 2 Screenshot of the Nevrolens VR Experience

XR software refinement use cases and results

The refinement of the two XR software applications followed the principle of “Diversity, Inclusivity, and Accessibility” of the XR4Human Code of Conduct, which advises to design immersive experiences that are inclusive and accessible to as many users as possible, considering their intended use and to ensure experiences also cater to the special needs of marginalized and vulnerable populations,

⁸ Nevrolens <https://www.ntnu.edu/imtel/nevrolens>

⁹ The development of the Nevrolens app has been supported by the Inclusive Peer Learning with Augmented Reality Apps - iPEAR project, partially funded by the European Union’s Erasmus Plus program, grant number [2020-1-DE01-KA203-005733](https://www.erasmus-plus.eu/en/grants-and-actions/2020-1-DE01-KA203-005733).

¹⁰ Mikhail Fominykh, Ekaterina Prasolova-Førland, Chryssa Themeli, Mathilde Haugum, Miriam Woldseth, Asbjørn Kallestad, Gabriel Kiss, and Kseniia Makhortova (2024): Peer Learning of Neuroanatomy with Augmented Reality: the Nevrolens application. International Conference on Cyberworlds (CW), Kofu, Japan, 2024, pp. 151-158, doi: [10.1109/CW64301.2024.00055](https://doi.org/10.1109/CW64301.2024.00055).

including people with disabilities and the economically disadvantaged. The refinements also enabled the evaluations presented earlier in Section 4.

Inclusion and Accessibility refinements in the VR4VET Blue Sector app

The first use case of refinements of the VR4VET Blue Sector app was originally planned along the following principles and practices of the XR4Human Code of Conduct:

- Social inclusion: Empowering vulnerable unemployed youth, emphasis on sustainable food production
- Human-centred design, user agency: User takes active role in exploring various professions, supporting user's choice competence
- Safe experience (mental health): Formative feedback and game mechanics, directed at users with low self-esteem, enhancing their sense of mastery

The refinement included improvements and new features following the XR4Human Code of Conduct:

- Accessibility, equitability, inclusion Automatic sound narration, appropriate written text information, using text-to-speech, configurable in the app settings.
- Accessibility, equitability, inclusion: An additional UI layout for visual impaired users with higher contrast and large font size, configurable in the app settings.
- Safe experience (physical health): An advanced tutorial, especially targeting users with low digital skills and those who use VR for the first time, focusing on help with the controllers and safety.

The second use case of refinements of the VR4VET Blue Sector app was originally planned to improve the non-player characters in the app. The originally implemented non-player characters provided only practical and instructional information without any adjustment to specific target groups and individual users. The information is presented in a form of structured dialogs, using text-to-speech. This use case focused on making the non-player characters more inclusive, using large language models for dialogs, as well training chatbots to conduct their conversations in accordance with ethical standards of professional career counsellors, working with vulnerable populations. The application features designed in accordance with XR4Human code of conduct:

- Social inclusion: Empowering vulnerable unemployed youth, emphasis on sustainable food production
- Human-centred design, user agency: User takes active role in exploring various professions, supporting user's choice competence
- Safe experience (mental health): Formative feedback and game mechanics, directed at users with low self-esteem, enhancing their sense of mastery

Features proposed for the development in accordance with XR4Human code of conduct:

- Interoperability, merging XR and AI technologies, something that will be highly relevant in the future, exploring the possibility of interfacing with different back-end solutions
- Safe experience (mental health), inclusion and user agency: chatbots developed with input from career counsellor researchers at NTNU will communicate with vulnerable users in a way that adheres to empowers them, enables them to make good career choices and adheres to general ethical standards for counselling

The results of the refinement of the VR4VET Blue Sector app are illustrated in a video¹¹ and include the following:

- **Tutorial:** An integrated and optional tutorial provides the user with the necessary guidance to comfortably use the application, interacting with objects, navigating, and interacting with the user interface.

Figure 3 Screenshot of the Tutorial Interface

- **Reception and general introduction:** The tutorial is a part of the Reception scene, where the user can get a general introduction to the thematic environment of the application. This improves the accessibility of the application improving the possibility of independent use.

¹¹ Accessibility and Inclusion features of the VR4VET Blue Sector app
<https://youtu.be/4g8QTCx0cmM>

Figure 4 Screenshot of the General Introduction

- The user has an option to activate **Controller Tooltips**. Throughout the application, all interactable objects will trigger tooltips which point to the exact button that the user should press on the VR controller to interact with this interactable object. This option can be deactivated for the more experienced users.

Figure 5 Screenshot of the Controller Tooltips

- **User Interface accessibility modes:** The user interface of the application is available in a normal mode and has two accessibility modes “high-contrast” and “large font size”, which can be changed in the Settings menu. These settings will be remembered next time you start the application. “High-contrast” and “large font size” features also affect the diegetic user interface

elements, like on this virtual tablet (see screenshot below), the display of this microscope, fish feeding information displays, and other objects.

Figure 6 Illustration of differences in contrast and text size (left is post and right is pre change)

- **Localization:** A localization system has been implemented, and most of the information in the app is available in two languages: English and Norwegian. The language of the application can be changed in the Settings menu. The choice will be remembered next time you start the application.

Figure 7 Example of localisation features

- **Text-to-speech:** The text-to-speech feature has been added to the app. The user can play the sound of most text information presented in the application. This includes many non-player characters that can talk.

Figure 8 Illustration of Text-to-speech

- **Non-player characters:** These non-player characters are present in every workplace environment of the Blue Sector app to provide step-by-step guidance to the job seekers who are using the application.

Figure 9 Illustration of Non-Playable Characters providing guidance

Inclusion and Accessibility refinements in the Nevrolens app

The Nevrolens app, developed in collaboration with Nobel Prize winning Kavli Institute for Systems Neuroscience has shown the potential to transform peer learning of neuroanatomy among neuroscience and medical students.

The third use case of refinements of the Nevrolens app was originally planned along the following principles and practices of the XR4Human Code of Conduct:

- Social inclusion and accessibility: access to neuroscience education everywhere and for everyone through multi-platform app
- Physical health (of people and animals): a part of the motivation behind the development of the app was originally to minimize COVID-19 exposure (remote learning with AR app) and reduce use of rat cadavers for dissection

Features proposed for the development in accordance with XR4Human code of conduct:

- Implementation of general improvements of the UX of the app based on the completed designs.
- Accessibility and user agency: Automatic sound narration all appropriate written text information, using text-to-speech, configurable in the app settings.
- Accessibility and user agency: An additional UI layout for visual impaired users with higher contrast and large font size, configurable in the app settings.

The results of the refinement of the Nevrolens app are illustrated in a video¹² and include the following:

- **User Interface re-design:** First, most of the User Interface has been re-designed for screen-space, evaluated with end users, and further improved based on the feedback. The user interface is high contrast with large fonts used for text elements, following the accessibility standards and best practices. The example screenshots below show a new curtain screen “Session” for the selection of brain models (on the left) and a new system for the whole brain manipulation interaction (round buttons on the right side of the screen of the rights screenshot).

¹² Accessibility and Inclusion features of the Nevrolens app
https://youtu.be/RrtD_yg79ro?si=5X_yeYMMfzKWAXuM

Figure 10 Illustration of the User Interface Re-Design

- Tutorial:** An integrated and optional tutorial provides the user with the necessary guidance to comfortably use the application, covering the most common misconceptions and needs in use discovered in user testing. The tutorial includes (a) the Understanding of the Augmented Reality space (see screenshot below on the left), (b) the manipulation controls for the entire brain model, (c) manipulating the individual sections of the brain model, and (d) accessing the information about these sections, including the text-to-speech feature (see screenshot below on the right).

Figure 11 NeuroLens Tutorial

- **Text-to-Speech:** Information about the different parts and sections of the brain is available as text. Interacting with a specific part of the brain in the AR space will display its name in the bottom panel of the app, which then can be extended to get a more detailed description (see screenshot below, on the left). Furthermore, by tapping on the Text-to-Speech button (left side of the screen on both screenshots below), the user can listen to the same description. The speech can be stopped at any time by tapping on the same Text-to-Speech button again. When working with both rat and human brain models placed in the same AR space, the user can interact with their parts and sections at the same time and in the same way (see screenshot below, on the right).

Figure 12 Implementation of Text to Speech

Conclusions of the software refinement

Both submissions are now presented within the Experience Library as examples of responsible and ethically aligned XR practice.

While the software refinements addressed immediate evaluation needs and demonstrated practical implementation of XR4HUMAN Code of Conduct principles, ensuring the long-term impact of these improvements requires a sustainable framework for the Experience Library. The next section outlines how the evaluation framework and refined applications will be maintained and expanded beyond the project's lifetime to continue supporting responsible XR development.

6 Sustainability plan for the Experience Library

The Experience Library will be sustained and further expanded beyond the lifetime of the project through integration with the XR4Europe web platform. In its future form, the library will be fully replicated on the XR4Europe website, retaining its current branding to preserve identity and recognition, while adopting a potentially refreshed visual style to align with XR4Europe's design framework. Functionality will remain consistent with the current implementation to ensure continuity for existing users. A direct link will be maintained from the XR4HUMAN website to the XR4Europe-hosted version, enabling seamless navigation between the two platforms.

The migration and integration process is planned for completion after the conclusion of the funded project period, ensuring that the necessary development, quality assurance, and stakeholder consultations are undertaken without disrupting ongoing project activities.

As part of this transition, the underlying data collection workflow will be adapted to move away from the current reliance on Qualtrics. The project team has identified a lightweight, flexible alternative in Tally. So, which offers simplified survey deployment, easier integration with the library, and lower long-term running costs. XR4Europe is already familiar with using Tally, having utilised it for more than a year for survey research and open calls, ensuring a smooth transition to this platform for future Experience Library submissions.

To maintain the integrity and value of the Experience Library after the project ends, a volunteer-based pool of evaluators will be established. This group will draw on the XR4HUMAN network as well as external collaborators from XR4Europe and other allied initiatives. The evaluator pool will operate under the coordination of Professor Oliver Schreer, co-lead of WP6 and a member of the XR4Europe Board of Directors, who will provide oversight on evaluation quality, methodological consistency, and recruitment of additional contributors. The application evaluation process will build on the ethical self-assessments created by the XR4HUMAN project. Evaluations will not be a static continuation of the process trialled and established during XR4HUMAN but will continue to evolve and to integrate the project's final outputs, namely the XR Code of Conduct, the Interoperability Guide, and the ethical self-assessment checklist.

Additionally, the scope of the Experience Library will undergo annual review in the year after the XR4HUMAN project to ensure it aligns with emerging trends and needs in the marketplace. Reviews may lead to modifications such as in the scope of projects considered and featured, the requirements for application, and the variety of communication and promotional channels used to support the selected projects. Annual reviews will be conducted online and will involve persons drawn from XR4HUMAN partners, the pool of expert application evaluators, and XR4Europe's management team.

Selected applications will remain in the Experience Library so long as they confirm the accuracy of their submissions. This helps to prevent the library becoming a repository of abandoned projects in the years to come. At the conclusion of the XR4HUMAN project, annual confirmation emails will be sent to the contacts registered for each selected submission. Subject to the Experience Library's annual review, confirmation will simply require explicit confirmation from submitters that their previously submitted information remains correct and accurate.

Conclusions

Task 6.4 set out to evaluate example use cases in ways that are technically informative, ethically grounded, and inclusive of user diversity. The work delivered on three fronts. First, it produced a literature-derived, expert-refined, modular post-experience survey that can travel across domains and populations while retaining construct comparability. Second, it demonstrated through deployments in public, laboratory, employment, accessibility, and clinical settings how evaluation must adapt to context without losing coherence. The emphasis throughout was on factors that matter for evaluation—onboarding, orientation and navigation, sensory and cognitive load, accessibility, vocational relevance, and engagement sustainability—rather than on product-level verdicts. Third, it established a sustainability pathway for the Experience Library, including integration with XR4Europe, adoption of a lighter data-collection platform, and a governance model for ongoing evaluation.

The Experience Library addresses gaps that existing catalogues and repositories rarely cover. It requires contributors to evidence accessibility, safety and ethical practice using a common instrument and self-assessment based on the XR4HUMAN Code of Conduct. Entries are described and, where feasible, evaluated against shared constructs, allowing users and practitioners to compare like with like across age groups, abilities and contexts. This gives practical value for organisations that serve vulnerable or under-represented users, providing clear indicators of onboarding demands, sensory load, navigation complexity, and available accessibility features before adoption decisions are made.

Beyond collation, the Library curates examples that have been iteratively improved for inclusion and documents how those changes affected usability and engagement. This transforms it from a static repository into a learning resource, where inclusive design decisions and their user impact are transparent. Its governance model further enhances this value: the volunteer evaluator pool, annual accuracy checks, and integration with XR4Europe processes maintain quality and avoid drift towards outdated or promotional content. Migration to a lightweight, low-cost platform and multilingual submission support also reduce entry barriers for smaller teams and community organisations, extending representation beyond well-resourced developers.

Together these outputs provide XR4HUMAN and its successors with a reusable framework for measuring user experience in XR that supports responsible innovation. The framework is sufficiently standardised for pooled analysis and benchmarking, yet flexible enough to respect differences of age, ability, setting and purpose. As XR adoption widens, a maintained Experience Library and living evaluation toolkit will enable the community to identify good practice quickly, surface risks early, and ensure the lived experience of diverse users remains at the centre of design and deployment.

Annex 1: Post-XR Experience Final Survey (Online Version)

Start of Block: Opening

Thank you for participating! Your feedback is valuable to us and for helping to improve the development of XR technology. Please take a moment to fill out this short survey. If you are unsure about the terminology used in any of these questions, please ask your demonstrator for guidance. This form was developed through European Union's Horizon Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101070155 and the UKRI through the Horizon Europe Guarantee (#10039307).

End of Block: Opening

Start of Block: Demographics

Age

- Aged 10 or under
 - 11-17
 - 18-29
 - 30-39
 - 40-49
 - 50-59
 - 60-69
 - 70 or older
-

Sex

- Male
 - Female
 - Non-Binary
 - Prefer not to say
-

Highest level of education

- Less than high school
 - High school graduate
 - Some college or vocational training
 - Bachelor's degree or higher
 - Prefer not to say
-

Visual Exceptionalities (please tick all that apply)

- No known visual impairments
 - Glasses or contact lenses for distance
 - Glasses or contact lenses for reading
 - Color vision deficiency (color blindness)
 - Low vision
 - Partially sighted
 - Blind in one eye
 - Fully blind
 - Other _____
 - Prefer not to say
-

Previous experience with XR

- Never tried before
 - Tried once or twice
 - Occasionally use (a few times a year)
 - Regular use (a few times a month)
 - Frequent use (weekly or more)
 - Expert or professional use
-

Auditory Exceptionalities (please tick all that apply)

- None
 - Hearing impairments
 - Hearing devices/aids
 - Other _____
 - Prefer not to say
-

Psychological Exceptionalities (please tick all that apply)

- Phobias to content: Arachnophobia, etc.
 - Phobias to environment: Vertigo, Thalassophobia, Astrophobia, etc.
 - Social Anxiety
 - None that I am aware of
 - Other _____
 - Prefer not to say
-

Page Break

What type of experience(s) did you try?

- Single Player
- Multiplayer
- Social VR

What type of device did you use? If unsure, please ask your demonstrator/experimenter. Tick all that apply.

- Smartphone/Tablet/Handheld-based VR/AR

- Standalone VR _____
- Tethered VR _____
- Augmented or Mixed Reality Glasses

- Desktop/Laptop _____
- Other _____

How enjoyable was the XR experience that you just tried?

- Not at all
- Somewhat
- Neutral
- Enjoyable
- Very Enjoyable

How easy was it to use, interact, and navigate the experience?

- Very Difficult
- Difficult
- Neutral
- Easy
- Very Easy

Did you experience any physical discomfort (e.g., dizziness, nausea)?

- Not at all
- A little
- Neutral
- Quite a bit
- A lot

Page Break

To what extent has this experience/session changed your expectations or perceptions of XR?

- Significantly Negatively Altered
- Slightly Negatively Altered
- No Change
- Slightly Positively Altered
- Significantly Positively Altered

What topic area(s) best describe your experience(s). Please tick all that apply.

- Entertainment and Gaming
- Education and Training
- Healthcare and Medicine
- Architecture and Design
- Retail and Shopping
- Tourism and Travel
- Culture and Art
- Social Interaction
- Work and Productivity
- News and Journalism
- Other _____

How concerned are you about data privacy and security in XR?

- Not Concerned at All
 - Slightly Concerned
 - Neutral / Unsure
 - Moderately Concerned
 - Extremely Concerned
-

How close do you think XR technology is to being ready for widespread, everyday use?

- Not close at all
 - Somewhat close
 - Neutral
 - Close
 - Very Close
-

I believe that the use of XR technologies can help me with my job prospects/career aspirations.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Not Sure
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

I see myself as someone who takes decisions when it comes to trying, purchasing or implementing new ICT technologies.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neither
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

End of Block: Demographics

Start of Block: Thank You

Thank you for completing this feedback. Your responses are very important to us. If you have any further questions, please contact:

End of Block: Thank You
